

ASSESSMENT OF PMFBY (PRADHAN MANTRI FASAL BIMA YOJANA) IN BEED DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

This study analyzes the growth and impact of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) from 2016-17 to 2022-23, using Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) to evaluate its performance and effects on the income stability of insured farmers. Conducted in four talukas of Beed district, Maharashtra, the research utilized secondary data for growth assessment and sampled 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers from 12 villages. Descriptive statistics and Garrett's Ranking Technique were employed to analyze income stability and identify challenges in Beed district. The findings show varying adoption rates of PMFBY across regions. In Maharashtra, the scheme saw a 20 per cent annual growth in insured farmers during the Kharif season, while the Rabi season experienced a 12 per cent decline. In Beed district, growth was marginal, with only a 2 per cent increase in Kharif and a 12 per cent decrease in Rabi, indicating significant barriers to participation. The income index improved from 0.78 (without compensation) to 0.81 (with compensation), demonstrating better financial stability when timely compensation is provided. Key constraints faced by insured farmers include insufficient compensation (mean score 75.5), delays in receiving payments (74.9), poor coordination between banks and farmers, lack of qualified experts for crop loss assessment, and frequent policy changes. Corruption and trust issues ranked lower in importance. Farmers' suggestions for improvement emphasized the need for timely compensation (63.33%), adequate compensation (53.33%), disbursement of claims before the next season (50.83%), and greater transparency from agencies (40%). In conclusion, the study highlights the need for policy reforms to boost farmer participation, address regional disparities, and streamline claims processes, particularly during the Rabi season. Improving PMFBY's efficiency is essential for enhancing income stability and overall effectiveness.

Keywords: PMFBY, CAGR, Income stability, challenges

Introduction

Agriculture is a cornerstone of India's economy, employing 44 per cent of the population and contributing 18.3 per cent to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). However, farmers face significant risks from natural disasters, pests, diseases, and unpredictable weather, resulting in substantial crop losses. Effective risk management, such as crop insurance, is crucial for stabilizing farmers' incomes and ensuring the sector's resilience. Crop insurance helps distribute financial risks across policyholders, allowing farmers to recover from losses. Insurance companies collect premiums to create a fund for compensating affected farmers, with risks spread over time and location. The Indian government has long recognized the importance of crop insurance. Early efforts began in 1920 with a rain insurance proposal in Mysore. In 1943, the Dewas Junior State introduced a compulsory crop insurance plan, but substantial progress occurred post-independence. The first major initiative came in 1972 with an individual farm-based insurance scheme for H-4 cotton. This was followed by the Pilot Crop Insurance Scheme (PCIS) in 1979, which introduced an area-based approach. The Comprehensive Crop Insurance Scheme (CCIS) in 1985 expanded coverage, with costs shared by central and state governments. In 1999, the National Agriculture Insurance Scheme (NAIS) replaced CCIS, offering better protection against natural calamities. A significant development was the launch of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in 2016, which aimed to address the shortcomings of earlier schemes. PMFBY offers low premium rates (2% for Kharif crops, 1.5% for Rabi, and 5% for commercial crops), using technology like remote sensing and drones to improve crop assessment and speed up claim settlements. However, challenges like moral hazard, administrative delays, and issues with enrolling small farmers remain. The study suggests that continuous monitoring, technological refinement, and improved outreach are key to enhancing PMFBY's implementation, stabilizing farmers' incomes, and promoting sustainable agriculture. Overall, crop insurance remains essential for managing risks and ensuring the long-term sustainability of India's agricultural sector.

Methodology

Beed district, known for its unique agricultural challenges, was chosen as the focus of this study. Four talukas were selected based on the performance of PMFBY, and within each of the 12 selected villages, 10 insured and 10 non-insured farmers were randomly surveyed,

totaling a sample of 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers. Data collection occurred during the Kharif season of 2023, combining both primary and secondary sources. Secondary data, essential for calculating the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR), was obtained from reports by Agriculture Insurance Company of India Limited and government websites. Key indicators analyzed included the number of insured farmers, total area insured, claims data, and beneficiaries, covering the period from 2016-17 to 2022-23. The CAGR was estimated using specific growth formulas.

$$Y_1 = a.b^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where,

Y = Dependent variable for which growth rate is to be estimated (Number of farmer insured / Area insured / Reported claim / Approved claim / Total claim paid / Total farmer benefitted)

t = Time variable

b = Regression coefficient

a = Intercept

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows

$$\log y = \log a + t \log b \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Then the per cent compound growth rate (r) was computed using the equation.

$$\text{CGR} (r) = [\text{Antilog} (\log b) - 1] \times 100 \dots\dots(3)$$

The significance of the regression coefficient was tested using the student's 't' test

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze income, including mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation (CV), and Income Stability Index. The Income Stability Index was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Income Stability Index} = 1 - \text{CV}$$

indicating income stability for both insured and non-insured farmers. The CV and income stability index allowed for a comparative analysis of income variation and stability between the two groups.

For identifying implementation weaknesses, Garrett's Ranking Technique was applied. Farmers ranked various challenges, and the ranks were converted into scores using Garrett's Table. Convert the ranks into Garrett scores using the following formula:

$$\text{Percent Position} = \left(\frac{R_{ij} - 0.5}{N_j} \right) \times 100$$

Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i^{th} factor by the j^{th} individual

N_j = Number of factors ranked by the j^{th} individual

These scores were then averaged to identify the most significant issues affecting PMFBY implementation in Beed district.

Results And Discussion

Progress of PMFBY

Compound Annual Growth Rate (Cagr) Of Insured Farmers

The data analysis on insured farmers reveals notable trends across regions and seasons. Nationally, the Kharif season saw a significant decline in insured farmers with a -7 per cent CAGR (t-value: -1.98), indicating barriers like high premiums or lack of awareness. The Rabi

season's decline of -2 per cent was less severe and statistically insignificant (t-value: -0.62). In Maharashtra, the Kharif season showed strong growth with a 20 per cent CAGR (t-value: 2.98), while Rabi saw a modest 3 per cent growth, but not statistically significant (t-value: 0.25). In Beed, Kharif had a minor 2 per cent growth (t-value: 1.83), and Rabi saw a concerning -12 per cent decline (t-value: -1.65). These findings point to a national decline, Maharashtra's success, and Beed's challenges, calling for targeted interventions.

Table 1: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Insured farmers under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-7%**
		t value	-1.98
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	20%**
		t value	2.98
3	Beed	CAGR	2%**
		t value	1.83

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Area Insured

The analysis of insured areas across regions and seasons reveals important agricultural insurance trends. Nationally, the Kharif season shows a slight 1% growth in insured area, though the t-value of 0.51 indicates this increase is not statistically significant. The Rabi season also has a 1 per cent growth with a t-value of 0.34, suggesting limited growth without statistical significance. In Maharashtra, Kharif shows a strong 19 per cent CAGR in insured area, indicating successful policies, though the t-value (1.34) is not statistically significant. Rabi's

4 per cent growth also lacks statistical significance (t-value: 0.29). In Beed, Kharif sees minor growth (1% CAGR, t-value: 0.83), while Rabi shows a concerning -5 per cent decline (t-value: -0.79), indicating challenges in insurance uptake. Overall, Maharashtra shows promising growth, while Beed faces difficulties, especially in Rabi, highlighting the need for region-specific interventions to boost insurance participation. These findings suggest that while growth is occurring, stronger efforts are needed to improve insurance coverage, particularly in areas like Beed.

Table 2: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Area of insured farmers under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	1%**
		t value	0.51
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	19%**
		t value	1.34
3	Beed	CAGR	1%**
		t value	0.83

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Reported claims

The analysis of reported agricultural insurance claims shows varied trends across India, Maharashtra, and Beed during the kharif and rabi seasons. Nationally, kharif claims exhibit a slight decline (CAGR: -1.52%), with a statistically significant t-value (2.41), indicating barriers like lack of awareness or distrust in the system. Conversely, rabi claims surge by 44 per cent, with a t-value of 1.75, suggesting greater farmer engagement due to heightened risks. In Maharashtra, kharif claims drop sharply by -41 per cent (t-value: -1.52), raising

concerns about disengagement, while rabi claims remain stable (1% CAGR, t-value: 0.04). Beed's kharif claims show a minor, non-significant decline (-1% CAGR, t-value: -0.11), but rabi claims face a significant drop of -37 per cent (t-value: -2.31), pointing to barriers in accessing the claims process. Overall, the findings highlight declining kharif claims nationally and in Maharashtra, while rabi claims rise at the national level but decline in Beed, signaling the need for improved farmer engagement and support.

Table 3: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Reported Claims under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	8%**
		t value	2.41
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-41%**
		t value	-1.52
3	Beed	CAGR	-1%**
		t value	-0.11

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Approved claims

The analysis of approved agricultural insurance claims in India, Maharashtra, and Beed reveals concerning trends for the kharif and rabi seasons. Nationally, the kharif season shows a dramatic decline of -60 per cent CAGR in approved claims, highlighting significant accessibility issues, with a statistically significant t-value of -2.47. The rabi season also declines by -26 per cent, but the t-value of -0.84 indicates this change is not statistically significant. In Maharashtra, kharif claims decrease by -42 per cent (t-value: -1.57), pointing to

similar concerns. Conversely, rabi claims exhibit a slight increase of 3 per cent, although the t-value of 0.11 suggests it's not significant. Beed experiences a negligible decline in kharif claims (-1% CAGR, t-value: -0.11) but faces a worrying -35% drop in rabi claims (t-value: -1.56), indicating barriers in the claims process. Overall, these trends reflect critical issues in the agricultural insurance system, particularly during the kharif season. The findings underscore the need for systemic reforms to improve claims approval efficiency and enhance farmer engagement and resilience against agricultural risks.

Table 4: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Approved Claims under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-60%**
		t value	-2.47
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-42%**
		t value	-1.57
3	Beed	CAGR	13%**
		t value	0.58

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total claim paid

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of claims disbursed under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) from 2016 to 2023 reveals key trends in compensation across India, Maharashtra, and Beed, highlighting differences between the kharif and rabi seasons. Nationally, kharif claims show a slight decline of -5 per cent CAGR, but the t-value of -1.01 indicates this change is not statistically significant. In contrast, rabi claims decline by -20 per cent CAGR, with a significant t-value of -2.35, pointing to increased challenges for farmers. In Maharashtra, kharif claims grow by 7 per cent CAGR,

though this is not significant (t-value: 0.83). Rabi claims decline by -13 per cent CAGR (t-value: -0.55), indicating potential engagement issues. Beed experiences a -11 per cent decline in kharif claims (t-value: -1.23), while rabi claims drop dramatically by -37 per cent (t-value: -2.31), signaling substantial barriers for farmers. Overall, these trends highlight urgent issues, especially in the rabi season, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to improve the effectiveness of the insurance system and enhance farmer support during agricultural distress.

Table 5: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total claim paid under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-5%**
		t value	-1.01
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	7%**
		t value	0.83
3	Beed	CAGR	-11%**
		t value	-1.23

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total farmers benefited

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of total farmer benefits under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) from 2016 to 2023 reveals significant trends in insurance benefits across India, Maharashtra, and Beed, particularly during the kharif and rabi seasons. Nationally, kharif benefits show a CAGR of -6 per cent, indicating a decline due to potential barriers in accessing support or inefficiencies in the claims process, with a statistically significant t-value of -3.02. The rabi season sees a more alarming drop of -19 per cent CAGR, emphasizing serious concerns regarding timely assistance for farmers, supported by a t-value of -2.41. In Maharashtra, kharif benefits slightly improve with a 1 per cent CAGR, though not statistically significant (t-value: 0.11). The rabi season matches the national trend with a -19

per cent decline but lacks statistical significance (t-value: -0.73). Beed experiences a negligible -1 per cent decline in kharif benefits (t-value: -0.11), while rabi benefits plummet by -35 per cent, indicating significant barriers with a t-value of -1.57. Overall, these findings highlight critical deficiencies in the PMFBY system, necessitating urgent reforms to enhance benefit distribution, particularly during the rabi season. While some improvement is noted in Maharashtra's kharif benefits, the overall trends indicate a pressing need for targeted interventions to improve access and support for farmers. The analysis aligns with previous research by Chanda and Srivastava (2022), suggesting that addressing operational bottlenecks is essential for the effectiveness of PMFBY.

Table 6: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total farmer benefited under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-6%**
		t value	-3.02
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	1%**
		t value	0.11
3	Beed	CAGR	-1%**
		t value	-0.11

Note: (**) Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

The impact of PMFBY on income stability of farmers

Gross income stability and income stability index of sample insured farmers

This analysis presents key metrics for gross yield comparisons between scenarios with and without compensation, including standard deviation, mean, coefficient of variation, and income index, offering insights into yield stability and financial performance. The standard deviation of gross yield without compensation is 17,985.21, indicating high variability. With compensation, it decreases to 16,943.62, suggesting increased yield stability. This reduction enhances financial planning and risk assessment, providing stakeholders with more consistent returns. The mean gross yield without compensation is 80,234.89, while with compensation, it rises to 88,523.72, an increase of 10,288.83. This highlights the positive impact of compensation on financial returns, likely due to better alignment of incentives among

stakeholders. The coefficient of variation improves from 0.22 without compensation to 0.19 with compensation, indicating lower relative variability in compensated yields. This is crucial for risk-averse investors, as it reflects a more predictable financial environment. The income index increases from 0.78 without compensation to 0.81 with compensation, signaling improved financial health and stakeholder satisfaction. A higher income index suggests that compensation mechanisms foster a more favourable economic climate. In summary, compensation mechanisms significantly enhance gross yield performance by increasing mean yield and income index while decreasing variability measures. These findings underscore the importance of effective compensation strategies for fostering stability and improving financial outcomes. Future research could explore optimal compensation models to maximize stakeholder engagement and success.

Table 7: Income stability index of sample insured farmers from year 2016-17 to 2022-23

Particulars	Gross income without compensation	Gross income with compensation
Standard Deviation	17985.21	16943.62
Mean	80234.89	88523.72
Coefficient of Covariation	0.22	0.19
Income Index	0.78	0.81

The weaknesses in implementation of PMFBY and suggest its improvement

Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers

The constraints faced by 120 insured farmers regarding the adoption of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) reveal significant barriers to its effectiveness. The most critical issue is insufficient compensation (Rank I), with a Garrett's Mean of 75.5, indicating that farmers find the compensation inadequate compared to their losses, impacting their financial stability and willingness to engage with the scheme. Delay in realization of compensation (Rank II) follows closely, with a mean of 74.9; these delays exacerbate financial challenges during crucial agricultural periods and undermine confidence in the program. The insufficient coordination between banks and farmers (Rank III), with a mean of 57.03, complicates the navigation of the insurance process, while the unavailability of qualified experts for crop loss assessment (Rank IV) (mean: 52.7) can lead to unfair compensation. Additionally, frequent changes in policy

terms (Rank V) create confusion (mean: 52.00), hindering compliance with claims requirements. Farmers also express a strong need for timely disbursement of claims (Rank VI) (mean: 48.05) to prepare for the upcoming planting season. Concerns about corruption in claims assessment and settlement (Rank VII) (mean: 39.55) further undermine trust in the PMFBY system, although perceived as less critical than other issues. The difficulty in trusting the scheme due to past experiences (Rank VIII) (mean: 31.90) affects engagement levels, while uncertainty regarding compensation after assessment (Rank IX) (mean: 34.15) leads to feelings of helplessness. Lastly, corruption issues rank lowest (Rank X) (mean: 23.1), indicating it is a concern but less critical compared to other constraints. In summary, the findings highlight that addressing the primary constraints insufficient compensation, payment delays, and inadequate coordination is crucial to enhancing PMFBY's reliability. Building trust through timely and fair compensation, clearer communication, and improved support systems will encourage greater farmer engagement and contribute to a more resilient agricultural sector.

Table 8: Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers (N=120) by Garretts ranking

Sr. no.	Constraints	Garrett's Mean	Garrett's Rank
1	Insufficient coordination of banks and farmers	57.03	III
2	Insufficient compensation under PMFBY	75.5	I
3	Delay in realization of compensation	74.9	II
4	corruption while assessment and settling claims	23.1	X
5	Frequent change in policy terms or condition create confusion while claim settlement	52.00	V
6	Experts are unavailable for assessment of crop loss	52.7	IV
7	Claim should be dispersed before starting of next season	48.05	VI
8	Hard to trust the scheme due to past experience	31.90	VIII
9	Even after assessment by agency there is no assurance of compensation	34.15	IX
10	Corruption while assessment and settling claims	39.55	VII

Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY

Suggestions from insured farmers for improving the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) based on their frequency, percentage, and rank. The most pressing need is timely compensation, ranked first with 76 responses (63.33%), emphasizing its critical role in effective financial management. Close behind is the demand for adequate compensation (Rank II), supported by 64 farmers (53.33%), indicating that the amount of compensation is as important as its timeliness for financial stability. The third suggestion calls for claims to be distributed before the next season (Rank III) from 61 farmers (50.83%), highlighting the need for timely claims to facilitate planning. Transparency from agencies ranks fourth (Rank IV, 48 responses, 40.00%), as farmers seek clarity in the decision-making process to foster trust. Other suggestions include improving agency operations (Rank VIII, 31 responses, 25.83%), ensuring uniform indemnity across regions (Rank VI, 43 responses, 35.83%), increasing the number of

crops covered (Rank VII, 39 responses, 32.50%), and providing insurance that includes price guarantees (Rank V, 46 responses, 38.33%). Lower priorities include raising awareness of the scheme (Rank X, 22 responses, 18.33%) and ensuring complete information on compensation (Rank IX, 23 responses, 19.17%). In summary, farmers highlight that both timely and adequate compensation are essential for the success of PMFBY. Delays in payment can severely impact financial stability, while insufficient compensation can leave farmers vulnerable. Additionally, transparency regarding claims processing and agency operations is crucial to build trust and improve farmer engagement with the PMFBY. Streamlining processes and enhancing communication can lead to a more efficient and responsive insurance experience. Addressing these suggestions collectively can significantly improve perceptions of PMFBY and contribute to a more resilient agricultural sector, fostering greater stability and productivity amidst uncertainties.

Table 9 : Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY

Sr.no.	Suggestions	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Adequate compensation	64	53.33	II
2	Timely compensation	76	63.33	I
3	Transparency from agencies	48	40.00	IV
4	Awareness of the scheme	22	18.33	X

5	Complete information on compensation	23	19.17	IX
6	Improved agency operations	31	25.83	VIII
7	Uniform indemnity for different regions and types of crops	43	35.83	VI
8	A greater number of crops are covered.	39	32.50	VII
9	Claims should be distributed before the start of the next season.	61	50.83	III
10	The insurance agency should offer insurance cover to include price guarantees.	46	38.33	V

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research highlights the positive impact of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) on insured farmers in Beed district, Maharashtra, particularly in stabilizing incomes against crop losses during the Kharif season. The scheme achieved a notable 2 per cent increase in insurance participation among farmers in Beed, with Maharashtra as a whole experiencing a substantial 20 per cent growth during the same season. However, the findings reveal a concerning 12 per cent decline in insured farmers during the Rabi season in Beed, indicating significant gaps in outreach and participation. While PMFBY has made important strides in protecting farmers and ensuring income stability, it faces challenges that require urgent attention. Key constraints include insufficient compensation, delays in claims processing, and inadequate coordination between banks and farmers. Addressing these issues is essential for enhancing the scheme's reliability and improving farmers' overall experience. Effective compensation mechanisms, which improve mean yield and income index while reducing variability, are crucial for fostering financial stability and resilience among farmers. To maximize the effectiveness of PMFBY, future research should explore optimal compensation models and strategies to increase stakeholder engagement. Building trust through timely and fair compensation, along with clearer communication and support systems, will further enhance participation in the scheme. By collectively addressing these challenges and suggestions, PMFBY can significantly improve perceptions among farmers and contribute to a more resilient agricultural sector, ensuring greater stability and productivity amidst uncertainties.

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